

EROSIVE - ULCER LESIONS OF THE GASTRODUODENAL ZONE IN PATIENTS WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS, THEIR DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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Purpose of the study: study of individual etiopathogenetic mechanisms and clinical features of erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastroduodenal zone in patients with liver cirrhosis and their correction.

Materials and research methods. 28 patients with liver disease were examined, in whom erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastroduodenal zone were detected by EGDS. All patients were divided into 2 groups: Group 1 received traditional therapy for the underlying disease (14 patients), Group 2, against the background of traditional therapy, received PPI pantoprazole (Pantap 40 mg) 1 capsule 2 times a day before meals for 28 days.

Research results. During examination of patients before treatment the following were revealed: astheno-neurotic syndrome - in 100% of patients, bloating - in 100% of patients, heaviness and pain in the right hypochondrium - in 78% of patients, nausea - in 52% of patients, bitterness in the mouth - in 43% of patients, yellowness of the skin - in 33% of patients, pain in the epigastrium - in 26% of patients, decreased appetite - in 24% of patients, vomiting - in 23% of patients, spider veins in 23% of patients, heartburn - in 14% of patients,

During ultrasound examination, all patients had changes in the liver: hepatomegaly in 55% of patients, decreased size in 15% of patients, splenomegaly in 45% of patients, dilation of the hepatic and splenic veins in 77% of patients.

Endoscopic examination revealed: gastric erosions in 59% of patients, duodenal erosions in 23% of patients, gastric ulcers in 15% of patients, duodenal ulcer in 3% of patients, duodenogastric reflux was detected in 87% of patients. After 15 days of treatment, erosions were absent in 70% of patients, ulcers healed in 46.8% of patients. In patients of group 1, a 1.0-fold decrease in the size of the ulcer and a 1.5-fold decrease in the number of mucosal erosions were observed only on days 10-15 of treatment.

Conclusions: 1. The clinical feature of hepatogenic ulcers is asymptomatic, low symptomatology.

2. The drug Pantap accelerates the regeneration of damage to the mucous membrane and is recommended for use in the complex therapy of erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastroduodenal zone in patients with liver cirrhosis.

